

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEES' ATTITUDES AND JOB PERFORMANCE IN LOCAL RETAIL BUSINESSES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between employees' attitudes and job performance among retail businesses in Dipolog City. Specifically, it assessed employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment, determined their perceived level of job performance, and analyzed the relationship between these variables. A quantitative correlational research design was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire administered to 175 randomly selected employees from 11 retail establishments. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Somers' D test. The findings revealed that employees reported a high level of job satisfaction ($M = 4.38$) and organizational commitment ($M = 4.29$), both interpreted as "Strongly Agree." Similarly, the level of job performance was high ($M = 4.42$), indicating strong performance in terms of productivity, teamwork, and quality of work. Further analysis showed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance ($D = 0.531$, $p < 0.001$) and between organizational commitment and job performance ($D = 0.471$, $p < 0.001$). The study concludes that employees' attitudes significantly influence job performance in retail settings. Enhancing job satisfaction and organizational commitment through supportive work environments, fair compensation, and career development opportunities may improve employee performance and overall organizational effectiveness.

Keyword: *job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job performance, retail sector, Dipolog City*

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is a critical factor in the success of retail businesses, particularly in local establishments where employees directly interact with customers and influence service quality and sales outcomes. In such settings, performance is not only determined by technical competence but is also shaped by employees' attitudes toward their work. Job satisfaction and organizational commitment are among the most influential factors affecting employees' motivation, behavior, and engagement, which ultimately impact performance (Mufti & Dewanto, 2025; Nurhasanah et al., 2025; Berhanu, 2023; Niuslie et al., 2022).

In an increasingly competitive and dynamic business environment, organizations recognize human resources as strategic assets essential for achieving organizational goals. As such, there is a growing emphasis on fostering a motivated, productive, and committed workforce. Organizational efforts such as providing continuous training, ensuring supportive work environments, offering fair compensation, and cultivating a positive organizational culture have been shown to enhance employees' job satisfaction and strengthen their commitment (Imaniyati et al., 2025). Employees who feel valued and supported are more likely to develop positive work attitudes, which translate into improved job performance and overall organizational effectiveness (Hussien et al., 2022).

Job satisfaction refers to an individual's subjective evaluation of their work experiences, encompassing feelings of fulfillment, recognition, and overall well-being derived from their job roles and work environment (Gumasing et al., 2023). Employees who perceive their work as meaningful and satisfying tend to demonstrate higher levels of productivity, engagement, and efficiency, as job satisfaction has been identified as a critical factor influencing job performance (Gazi et al., 2024). Meanwhile, organizational commitment reflects the psychological attachment, identification, and loyalty employees develop toward their organization, including their willingness to exert effort and remain part of the organization (Maravilla & Tuble, 2025; Morais, 2024; Nuñez Jr., 2025). Employees with high levels of commitment are more likely to contribute actively to organizational goals, demonstrate sustained effort, and maintain long-term involvement, thereby enhancing overall organizational effectiveness (Pulungan & Tiarapuspa, 2025; Herminingsih & Wartikah, 2025).

Despite extensive literature establishing the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee performance, a critical gap remains in the context of small and local retail businesses, particularly in developing regions such as Dipolog City and the broader Zamboanga Peninsula. Most existing studies are concentrated in large corporations or urban-based industries, where organizational systems, resources, and workforce structures differ significantly from those of small enterprises (Jindal et al., 2024; Otoo & Rather, 2024). There is limited empirical evidence that captures how job satisfaction and organizational commitment jointly influence employee performance within small-scale retail settings characterized by informal management practices, resource constraints, and close interpersonal working relationships (Riyanto et al., 2021). Moreover, studies conducted in developing

economies highlight the need for localized research, as findings from developed contexts may not fully apply to regional and socio-cultural conditions (Khan et al., 2024). In particular, localized studies reflecting the socio-economic and cultural dynamics of retail employees in Region IX remain scarce, thereby limiting the applicability of generalized findings to local business contexts.

Addressing this gap is essential for generating context-specific insights that can guide retail business owners, managers, and policymakers in improving employee management practices. In service-oriented environments such as retail, maintaining employees who are both satisfied and committed is crucial for sustaining service quality and operational efficiency. Hence, this study aims to examine the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee performance among local retail businesses in Dipolog City, providing empirical evidence that may serve as a basis for developing strategies to enhance workforce engagement, productivity, and organizational sustainability, this year 2025..

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine employees' attitudes and job performance among retail businesses in Dipolog City, this year 2025.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Highest educational attainment
 - 1.4 Job Position;
 - 1.5. Number of Years Working in the establishment; and
 - 1.6. Type of Retail Business?
2. What is the level of employees' attitudes in terms of:
 - 3.1 Job satisfaction; and
 - 3.2 Organizational commitment?
3. What is the level of employees' job performance?
4. Is there a significant relationship between employees' attitudes and their job performance?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative correlational research design to examine the relationship between employees' attitudes and job performance in retail businesses in Dipolog City. Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire administered to employees from selected retail establishments, including department stores, supermarkets, convenience stores, and other small retail shops. The population consisted

of 311 employees from 11 retail businesses, and a sample of 175 respondents was determined using Slovin's Formula with a 5% margin of error. Simple random sampling was utilized to ensure that each employee had an equal chance of being selected, thereby enhancing the representativeness of the sample. The research instrument was a modified questionnaire adapted from Dalkrani and Dimitriadis (2018) and Wiedower (2001), consisting of four parts: demographic profile, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job performance. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The instrument underwent reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.8802 for job satisfaction, 0.9659 for organizational commitment, and 0.6637 for job performance, indicating acceptable to high internal consistency. Prior to data collection, permission was secured from relevant authorities and store management. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and provided voluntary consent before completing the questionnaire. Ethical standards such as confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw were strictly observed throughout the study. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages to describe respondent profiles, weighted mean to determine the levels of employees' attitudes and job performance, and Somers' D test to assess the significant relationship between the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the responses of the one hundred seventy-five randomly selected employees from retail stores in Dipolog City. The collected data were statistically analyzed to describe the respondents' demographic profile and key study variables. Results were organized and presented in a clear and systematic manner, with tables used to facilitate better understanding and interpretation of the findings.

Table 1 indicates that the majority of retail employees in Dipolog City were young adults, with more than half (53%) aged 23–28 and an additional 31% aged 29–34. Only a small proportion of respondents were aged 18–22 (5%) or 35 years and above (11%). These findings suggest that the retail workforce in the area is predominantly composed of individuals in their early to mid-adulthood. This age distribution may be attributed to the dynamic and demanding nature of retail work, which often requires adaptability, energy, and continuous learning. Consistent with the findings of Topino et al. (2021), younger employees tend to prioritize career development and skill acquisition, making them more responsive to the fast-paced environment of retail settings. In contrast, older employees are more likely to value job stability and work–life balance, which may influence their levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Furthermore, as employees age, their work priorities tend to shift from rapid career advancement toward maintaining performance quality and efficiency, reflecting differences in motivation across age groups.

Table 1.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Age Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City

Age	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percent (%)
18-22 years old	8	5
23-28 years old	92	53
29-34 years old	55	31
35 years old and above	20	11
Total	175	100

Table 2 shows that retail stores in Dipolog City had a slightly higher proportion of female employees (54%) compared to male employees (42%), while a smaller percentage (4%) identified as other genders. This indicates that women comprised the majority of the workforce in the retail sector, reflecting a diverse employee composition. This finding is consistent with the study of Ahmed et al. (2022), which emphasized that women tend to dominate retail employment due to the sector's strong reliance on customer interaction and service-oriented roles. Although men and individuals of other gender identities also contributed to the workforce, their representation remained comparatively lower.

Table 2.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Sex Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City

Sex	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percent (%)
Male	73	42
Female	95	54
Other	7	4
Total	175	100

Table 3 presents the educational attainment of employees in retail stores in Dipolog City. The results show that 40% of employees were high school graduates, representing the largest group, followed by 33% who were college graduates and 27% who were college undergraduates. These findings indicate that the retail workforce is generally educated, with a considerable proportion having attained or pursuing higher education. This suggests that retail establishments in Dipolog City value educational qualifications in hiring, as these contribute to improved communication, customer service, and adaptability in a service-oriented environment. This finding is supported by Hyun et al. (2025), who emphasized the importance of educational attainment in enhancing employee competencies in the retail sector. Furthermore, Orbeta et al. (2021) noted that college experience is associated with better employability and overall job-related outcomes.

Table 3.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Highest Educational Attainment Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City

Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
High School Graduate	70	40
College Undergraduate	47	27
College Graduate	58	33
Total	175	100

Table 4 shows the distribution of retail store employees in Dipolog City according to their job positions. The largest group, making up 40.6% (71 individuals), consists of Sales Ladies and Sales Boys, reflecting their dominance in the retail workforce. Cashiers/Staff follow closely, comprising 32.6% (57 individuals). Utility workers represent 20% (35 individuals), while only 6.9% (12 individuals) hold Supervisory or Managerial roles, indicating a limited presence in leadership positions. The findings suggest that most employees in the retail sector are engaged in operational and customer-facing roles, with fewer assigned to managerial responsibilities. In support, Kotzé & Mostert (2025) pointing the fact that retail organizations rely heavily on frontline employees (FLEs) who directly interact with customers and perform core service functions, with managers primarily serving supervisory and strategic roles. Similarly, recent research emphasizes that frontline personnel represent the “face of retail,” playing a central role in customer service and daily operations, thereby reflecting the dominance of operational roles over managerial positions in the sector

Table 4.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Job Position Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City

Job Position	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Cashier/Staff	57	32.60
Supervisory/Managerial Position	12	6.80
Sales Lady/Sales Boy	71	40.60
Utility	35	20.00
Total	175	100

Table 5 presents the distribution of employees based on their years of employment in their current company. The majority of respondents, 47% (82 employees), had been employed for 2–3 years, followed by 38% (67 employees) with less than 2 years of tenure. A smaller proportion, 13% (22 employees), had worked for 4–5 years, while only 2% (4 employees) had more than 6 years of service. This distribution indicates a concentration of employees in the early years of employment, suggesting limited long-term retention within retail stores. The findings imply that although there is a steady influx of new hires, sustaining long-term employment remains a challenge. This is consistent with Pienaar et al. (2025), who reported that the retail sector is characterized by high employee turnover, with employees frequently leaving due to job demands and workplace conditions.

Table 5.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Employment Tenure Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City

Years of Employment	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Less than 2 years	67	38
2-3 years	82	47
4-5 years	22	13
6 years and above	4	2
Total	175	100

Table 6 shows the distribution of employees in retail stores in Dipolog City by business type. Department stores employ the largest share, at 36% (63 employees), followed by hardware stores at 29.7% (52 employees) and convenience stores at 18.9% (33 employees). Supermarkets account for 10.9% (19 employees), while other types of retail businesses make up the smallest group, at 4.6% (8 employees). This data indicates that department and hardware stores dominate the retail employment landscape in Dipolog City, while supermarkets and niche retail businesses play a smaller role. In support, Guinto and Magallanes (2020) stressing that retail employment in the Philippines is largely concentrated in department and hardware stores, which employ more workers due to their wider product range and operational scale, while supermarkets and niche retail businesses tend to have fewer employees.

Table 6.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Employees' Profile Among Retail Stores in Dipolog City by Type of Retail Business

Retail Businesses	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Department Store	63	36.0
Supermarket	19	10.9
Hardware Stores	52	29.7
Convenience Stores	33	18.9
Other (Specify)	8	4.6
Total	175	100

Table 7.
Mean and Description of Level of Employees' Attitude in Terms of Job Satisfaction

Statements	Employees' Attitude as to Job Satisfaction	
	Mean	Description
1. I understand how my job contributes to the achievement of the strategic goals of the company.	4.50	Strongly Agree
2. Through my work, my personal ambitions are met.	4.35	Strongly Agree

3. I use important skills and my ability to perform my work.	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. The training provided me to develop my skills and knowledge.	4.44	Strongly Agree
5. My workload is satisfactory.	4.38	Strongly Agree
6. I feel that my pay is fair for the work I offer.	4.27	Strongly Agree
7. The benefits I derive are better than those offered by other companies.	4.26	Strongly Agree
8. Additional economic benefits (bonus) are satisfactory.	4.38	Strongly Agree
9. The training provided me a factor for advancement or increased financial reward me.	4.37	Strongly Agree
10. There are significant chances for advancement in my work.	4.41	Strongly Agree
11. There are equal opportunities for all employees.	4.35	Strongly Agree
12. Those who carry out their work properly are more likely to development.	4.34	Strongly Agree
13. The company has a good workforce.	4.41	Strongly Agree
14. The business that I work for is known as a good employer locally.	4.45	Strongly Agree
15. I am satisfied from the natural environment of the company.	4.42	Strongly Agree
16. Communication in the business that I work for ranges to satisfactory levels.	4.43	Strongly Agree
17. There are relationships among colleagues of different parts.	4.22	Strongly Agree
18. There are relationships among colleagues of the same Department.	4.21	Strongly Agree
19. The company assumes responsibility for the society.	4.45	Strongly Agree
20. The company assumes responsibility for the environment.	4.39	Strongly Agree
21. The company has strong future growth prospects.	4.41	Strongly Agree
22. The company outperforms its competitors.	4.38	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.38	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree; 2.61 – 3.40 Neutral; 3.41 – 4.20 Agree; 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 7 presents the level of employees' attitudes in terms of job satisfaction. The overall average weighted mean of 4.38, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicates that employees in retail stores in Dipolog City demonstrated a high level of job satisfaction. All indicators fell within the "Strongly Agree" range, reflecting consistently positive perceptions across various dimensions of their work. The highest mean score (4.55) was recorded for "I use important skills and my ability to perform my work," suggesting that employees strongly perceived their competencies as effectively utilized. This was followed by "I understand how my job contributes to the achievement of the strategic goals of the company" (4.50), indicating strong role clarity and alignment with

organizational objectives. Items related to organizational reputation and social responsibility, such as *“The business is known as a good employer locally”* and *“The company assumes responsibility for society”* (both 4.45), were also highly rated. In contrast, slightly lower—though still high—mean scores were observed in *“There are relationships among colleagues of the same department”* (4.21) and *“There are relationships among colleagues of different parts”* (4.22), suggesting that interpersonal relationships, while positive, were comparatively less strong than other aspects. The findings indicate that employees were highly satisfied with their job roles, working conditions, compensation, opportunities for advancement, and organizational environment. This level of satisfaction reflects a supportive workplace that may foster higher motivation, engagement, and productivity among employees. These results are consistent with recent studies by Shrivastava and Mehta (2025) and Nizamuddin and Mokhtar (2024), which reported that high job satisfaction is significantly associated with increased motivation, engagement, and employee performance. Furthermore, a supportive work environment and adequate compensation were found to enhance job satisfaction, ultimately contributing to improved productivity and organizational effectiveness, particularly in service-oriented sectors such as retail.

Table 8.
Mean and Description of Level of Employees’ Attitude in Terms of Work Commitment

Statements	Employees’ Attitude as to Job Satisfaction	
	Mean	Description
1. I can trust my organization.	4.34	Strongly Agree
2. I suggest my friends to work at the same organization.	4.20	Agree
3. I'm willing to make great efforts to help the organization to succeed.	4.38	Strongly Agree
4. I feel proud when I tell others that I belong to this organization.	4.25	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.29	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree; 2.61 – 3.40 Neutral; 3.41 – 4.20 Agree; 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 8 presents the level of employees’ attitudes in terms of work commitment. The overall average weighted mean of 4.29, interpreted as “Strongly Agree,” indicates that employees demonstrated a high level of organizational commitment. This suggests that respondents exhibited strong attachment, loyalty, and willingness to contribute to the success of their organization. Among the indicators, the highest mean (4.38) was recorded for *“I’m willing to make great efforts to help the organization to succeed,”* reflecting a high level of dedication and proactive engagement. This was followed by *“I can trust my organization”* (4.34), indicating a strong foundation of trust, which is essential for sustaining commitment. Likewise, *“I feel proud when I tell others that I belong to this organization”* (4.25) highlights employees’ positive emotional attachment and sense of belonging. In contrast, the lowest mean (4.20), interpreted as “Agree,” was observed in *“I suggest my friends to work at the same organization,”* suggesting that although

employees held favorable perceptions of their organization, their level of advocacy was relatively less pronounced. Overall, the findings imply that employees possessed a high degree of work commitment characterized by trust, pride, and willingness to exert effort for organizational success. This level of commitment may contribute positively to employee retention, performance, and overall organizational effectiveness. These findings are supported by recent studies of Shrivastava and Mehta (2025) and Okongo et al. (2024), which reported that employees with high organizational commitment tend to demonstrate better performance and stronger retention. Moreover, organizational commitment has been found to have a significant positive relationship with job satisfaction, motivation, and employee performance, thereby enhancing productivity and service quality, particularly in service-oriented sectors such as retail.

Table 9.
Mean and Description of Perceived Level of Employees' Job Performance

Statements	Employees' Level of Job Performance	
	Mean	Description
1. I complete tasks and projects within the time frame expected.	4.39	Strongly Agree
2. I coordinate with others effectively to ensure timely completion of work.	4.42	Strongly Agree
3. I maximize available time by efficiently organizing my work schedule.	4.46	Strongly Agree
4. My work is consistently neat and well-organized.	4.42	Strongly Agree
5. The results I produce are accurate and dependable.	4.45	Strongly Agree
6. I pay careful attention to detail in my work.	4.42	Strongly Agree
7. I produce a high volume of work under normal conditions.	4.41	Strongly Agree
8. The amount of work I complete meets or exceeds expectations.	4.40	Strongly Agree
9. I handle a heavy workload efficiently.	4.35	Strongly Agree
10. I take initiative and require minimal intervention from supervisors.	4.41	Strongly Agree
11. I work independently and handle problems effectively on my own.	4.39	Strongly Agree
12. I contribute positively to a cooperative and supportive work environment.	4.46	Strongly Agree
13. I help to promote a sense of goodwill and respect among my co-workers and leaders.	4.43	Strongly Agree
14. I communicate effectively and respectfully with others, enhancing team morale.	4.49	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.42	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree; 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree; 2.61 – 3.40 Neutral; 3.41 – 4.20 Agree; 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 9 presents the perceived level of employees' job performance. The overall average weighted mean of 4.42, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicates that

employees in retail stores in Dipolog City demonstrated a high level of job performance. All indicators fell within the “Strongly Agree” range, reflecting consistently strong performance across various work dimensions. The highest mean score (4.49) was recorded for “*I communicate effectively and respectfully with others, enhancing team morale,*” highlighting strong interpersonal and communication skills. This was followed by “*I maximize available time by efficiently organizing my work schedule*” and “*I contribute positively to a cooperative and supportive work environment*” (both 4.46), indicating effective time management and teamwork. Moreover, “*The results I produce are accurate and dependable*” (4.45) underscores employees’ competence and attention to quality. In contrast, the relatively lower—though still high—mean score was observed in “*I handle a heavy workload efficiently*” (4.35), suggesting that while employees generally perform at a high level, managing heavier workloads may present a comparatively greater challenge. Overall, the findings indicate that employees demonstrated strong job performance in terms of productivity, quality of work, teamwork, and initiative. This suggests that employees are capable, efficient, and contribute positively to organizational goals, thereby enhancing overall workplace effectiveness and service delivery in retail establishments. These findings are supported by recent studies of Nguyen et al. (2025) and Hidayaturrohmah et al. (2025), which reported that satisfied and engaged employees tend to be more capable, efficient, and aligned with organizational goals. Furthermore, higher job satisfaction is significantly associated with improved work performance, productivity, and employee loyalty, ultimately enhancing organizational effectiveness. In retail settings, satisfied employees also contribute to better service quality and customer satisfaction, reinforcing their critical role in achieving organizational success.

Table 10.
Test of Relationship Between Respondents' Level of Attitude and Respondents' Perceived Level of Job Performance

Employees' Level of Attitude	Perceived Level of Job Performance		
	D-value	p-value @ 0.05*	Interpretation
Job Satisfaction	0.531	0.000	Significant
Commitment	0.471	0.000	Significant

*p-value < 0.05 level of significance = significant; Fail to accept H_0 .

*p-value > 0.05 level of significance = not significant; Accept H_0 .

Table 10 presents the test of relationship between employees’ level of attitude and their perceived level of job performance. The results indicate that job satisfaction had a moderate positive relationship with job performance, as reflected by a D-value of 0.531 and a p-value < 0.001, which is below the 0.05 level of significance. This denotes a statistically significant relationship, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Similarly, organizational commitment demonstrated a moderate positive relationship with job performance, with a D-value of 0.471 and a p-value < 0.001, also indicating statistical significance. These findings suggest that higher levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment are associated with better job performance among employees in retail stores in Dipolog City. Employees who are more satisfied with their jobs and more committed to their organization tend to perform their tasks more effectively and efficiently. Overall, the results underscore the critical role of employee attitudes in influencing job

performance, highlighting that fostering satisfaction and commitment can lead to improved organizational outcomes. These findings are consistent with recent studies by Nguyen et al. (2025), which reported that job satisfaction and organizational commitment significantly predict employee performance and organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, evidence shows that satisfied and committed employees demonstrate higher productivity, stronger retention, and greater contributions to organizational success.

Conclusions

This study examined the relationship between employees' attitudes—specifically job satisfaction and organizational commitment—and job performance among retail employees in Dipolog City. The findings revealed that the retail workforce is predominantly composed of young, relatively educated individuals engaged in operational and customer-facing roles, with limited representation in managerial positions. Moreover, the results indicated a concentration of employees within the early years of employment, suggesting challenges in long-term retention within retail establishments.

In terms of employees' attitudes, the study found that respondents demonstrated a high level of job satisfaction and organizational commitment, as reflected in their strong agreement across all indicators. Employees reported positive perceptions regarding their roles, working conditions, compensation, opportunities for advancement, and organizational environment. Similarly, employees exhibited strong commitment characterized by trust, pride, and willingness to contribute to organizational success.

Furthermore, employees demonstrated a high level of job performance, particularly in communication, teamwork, time management, and quality of work. These findings indicate that employees are capable, efficient, and able to contribute positively to organizational goals and service delivery.

Most importantly, the study established that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant and moderate positive relationship with job performance. This implies that employees who are more satisfied and committed tend to perform better in their respective roles. The results highlight the critical role of employee attitudes in enhancing performance and achieving organizational effectiveness.

In conclusion, fostering a supportive work environment that promotes job satisfaction and strengthens organizational commitment is essential for improving employee performance in retail businesses. These findings provide valuable insights for retail managers and business owners in developing strategies that enhance employee engagement, productivity, and long-term organizational sustainability in local retail settings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that retail business owners and managers enhance job satisfaction by improving working conditions, ensuring fair and competitive compensation, and maintaining a supportive work environment. Organizations should also strengthen organizational commitment by promoting employee engagement through recognition programs, open communication, and team-building activities that foster trust and a sense of belonging. Given the importance of skill utilization and growth, continuous training and clear career development opportunities should be provided to sustain motivation and improve long-term retention. Furthermore, efforts should be made to improve interpersonal relationships among employees by encouraging collaboration, teamwork, and positive workplace interactions. Considering the observed challenges in employee retention, management should implement strategies such as incentives, career advancement plans, and supportive leadership to retain employees for longer periods. To sustain high levels of job performance, organizations should continue providing performance feedback, recognition, and adequate resources that support productivity and service quality. Finally, future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables such as leadership style, work-life balance, and organizational culture, as well as extend the study to other sectors and locations to further validate and enrich the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with established ethical principles for research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was obtained from relevant authorities and retail store management. All respondents were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature of their participation, and informed consent was secured before administering the questionnaire. Participants were assured that their responses would be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. To protect anonymity, no personally identifiable information was collected, and all data were reported in aggregate form.

Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and respondents were given the right to decline or withdraw at any stage without any consequences. The study adhered to the principles of respect for persons, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice, ensuring that no harm was inflicted and that participants' rights and dignity were upheld throughout the research process. All collected data were securely stored and accessed only by the researchers. No conflict of interest was declared by the researchers in the conduct of this study. In addition, the researchers utilized artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as QuillBot solely for language editing, paraphrasing, and grammar refinement. These tools were used only to improve the clarity and organization of the manuscript and did not influence the research design, data collection, statistical analysis, or interpretation of results. All AI-assisted outputs were carefully reviewed, verified, and finalized by the

researchers to ensure accuracy, originality, and adherence to academic integrity standards.

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